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Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector in Pune - An Empirical Study

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ABSTRACT:

Training is a learning process which never ends. Training and development program helps the organization and the employee to become more productive and enhance the productive of the company and to develop the skill, knowledge and attitude of the employee which helps the organization to reach the goal. This study aims to study the impact of the training on Performance of the employees. There are various factors like Training and Development, Motivation, Behaviour, Attitude, Nature of the employee, working environment etc helps the organization to identify itself in a different image. Training and Development has a major role on it. there is a positive relationship in between the employee performance and the training with Motivation and organization productivity. This study concludes that the organization having good training programs for employee can enhance the performance of the employee. All the organization want to develop their employee performance should focus on training as it is also motivate employees to achieve higher performance level. Training and Development impact of a good training program depends upon understand the need of the employee and accordingly they design and implement it. Training and Development program also helps to enhance the productivity, revenue and profit of the organization. Continuous improvement is highly effective on the employee performance. Training and Development helps and develop the employee knowledge, skill and attitude while improving the Brand of the organization as well. This is the reason an ideal organization plans and implement the training and development program to stand and fulfill their goals and objectives. The focus of current study is to understand the impact of Training and Development, and its impact on motivation and productivity in Manufacturing

sector in Pune. It means it increases the overall organizational performance. We also prove our Hypothesis through empirical data. However, results are strongly based on the literature review. The data was collected through a structured questionnaire from different IT companies in Pune. The analysis was done through using the T Test and Annova through SPSS and some of the analysis was done thought the help of Excel.

KEY WORDS

Motivation, Employee Performance, Productivity,

INTRODUCTION

Motivation is the most significant element for all manufacturing companies which play a significant role for the accomplishment of any organization. Motivation is the important factor for the employee to motivate themselves in various ways which directly impact upon the performance and employee productivity. it also shows the results of the company and indicates the revenue in a proper manner. Training and Development program enhances the motivation level of the employee to fulfill their knowledge, skill. Besides of that it helps the organization to identify itself in a better way. The employee should understand their hard work and every individual should act on it. The motivation factor is vary from employee to employee. The role of the training and development program to motivate the entire employee, which impact upon the company productivity. Employee motivation is a reflection of the level of energy, commitment, and creativity that a company's workers bring to their respective job.

Training results into increase in productivity, reducing cost of operations, and improving overall efficiency. Goals can be achieved if coordination and cooperation takes place in working environment which can be effectively done through motivation. And Motivation will creates from Impact of training program arrange by the company as per requirement. The employees can remain loyal to the enterprise only when they have a feeling of participation in the management. The skills and efficiency of employees will always be of advantage to employees as well as employees. This will lead to a good public image in the market which will attract competent and qualified people into a concern.

There is a positive relationship between the employee performance and training and Development program and motivation of the employee. The organization having good and organized training program for employees can enhance the performance of the employee and helps the company productivity. The HR department has a vital role to play to motivate their employee for company benefit. The Department should have been emplhasizing on ensuring the continuous learning and development program for their employee and also be focusing on

ensuring on the ground of implementation of knowledge. In Manufacturing sector it is very necessary a proper training program, because the employees deliver their performance in a proper manner. It needs the motivational spirit, hard work and sincerity of the organization and the efficiency as well. The advancement of technology coupled with the rising expectations of the clients have made it mandatory for the Manufacturing sector to establish training mechanisms that would up skill their employees at regular intervals. For training interventions to be truly successful, the training enablers must therefore insist on ensuring a seamless training transfer process in the organization.

Detailed Relationship Cycle of the employee training and its productivity may be shown like below figure

Fig-1 Detailed Relationship cycle of Employee Training and Productivity

(Source:- Inter science Management Review (IMR) ISSN: 2231-1513 Volume-2, Issue-2, 2012)

The success of the organization depends upon its employee performance. So Training and Development program is required to fulfill the objectives. It is required for the sake of developing the employee performance and productivity and helps to develop the motivation as well. The focus is placed the impact of the training and development which deals with knowledge, skill and attitude in higher level of royalty and adds to the maximization of the productivity of the company. Training and Development offer competitive advantage to a firm by removing performance deficiencies; making employees stay long; scrap and damage; and

meeting future employee need. One effective method is to track training benefits by analyzing operational results to establish such things as whether the cost of training is outweighed by benefits, or whether training has impacted specific business factors.

OBJECTIVES

1. To examine the Impact of Training on Motivation in Manufacturing Sector
2. To find out the Impact of Training on employee Performance through Motivation.
3. To Examine the Training and Development on Employee Performance and Productivity in the context of Manufacturing on Class.
4. To Study employee Satisfaction and Productive with respect of Training and Development

LITERATURE REVIEW

Rani & Merga (2016) stated that, the system which approaches the company on training and development and apply on its productivity is more important. The major finding of the research shows that the system approach can be used on employee training program empirically which helps to get and develop the knowledge, skill and helps for productivity of the company.

Uzma Hafeez (2015), stated that, there is an impact of employee performance. Employees are the major assets of every organization, the accomplishment of the company depends on its employee performance. Hence the Management plan to arrange the Training program to enhance the knowledge and skill of the employee and to plan for develop the productivity of the company to fulfill the goal of the organization.

Rashad Yazdanifard (2013) stated that training has become is an essential part in the competitive market. Institute investing in effective training program for their employee tend to achieve both short and long term benefit to fulfill their objectives. He stated that, Learning and Development enhances the Motivation and develop their performance level which directly proposed to the productivity of the company. training and development is an instrument which

can be used for the purpose of development of the company. Hence Training and Development is vital role to the productive of the organizational workforce.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research design used for the purpose of research only. It is stratified random sampling method was taken to selected the respondents from various Manufacturing sector in Pune 150 Respondents have given their valuable feedback. A questionnaire was designed in a proper manner to find out the objectives.

The questionnaire was divided in to two major parts. Part I related to the different demographic factors and Part II was prepared to the different questions related to impact of training on Motivation and also related to performance and productivity of the company. The data was used to test the result and statistical test used to measure relationship between the selected variables. the data was analysed using the T Test and ANNOVA through SPSS and some of the data was analysed through the help of Excel.

HYPOTHESIS

H₀: There is no impact of demographic factors on Evaluation of the Impact of Learning & Development on Motivation , Employee Performance & Productivity in Manufacturing Sector

H₁: There is impact of demographic factors on Evaluation of the Impact of Learning & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in Manufacturing Sector

LIMITATION

The Primary data was collected for research purpose only from Manufacturing sectors from Pune City. There was a structured Questionnaire was prepared for the same and the data was collected from different Manufacturing Companies in Pune City.

FINDING

Table 1 :- Perception of Respondents on Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector (Content wise Analysis)

Sr No	Content	Yes	Percentage (%)	No	Percentage (%)
1	Do you think Training program helps to improve the Motivation, enhance the skills, knowledge and Attitude and behavior which helps the productivity?	144	96.00	6	4.00
2	Do you feel Training and Development helps the company to achieve more productivity to achieve the goal?	141	94.00	9	6.00
3	Does your company have any specific policy to provide the Training Program?	137	91.33	13	8.67
4	Do you think Motivation helps to improve the performance?	136	90.67	14	9.33
5	Does your company arrange some Training program to motivate the employee?	133	88.67	17	11.33
6	Do you think Motivation is an Essential part for employee & Organization?	130	86.67	20	13.33
7	Does your company provide Suitable Training program to enhance the Skill and knowledge of the employee ?	129	86.00	21	14.00
8	Do you think training results to make you more productive?	125	83.33	25	16.67
9	Does your company have any policy to measure the Training program?	124	82.67	26	17.33
10	Do you think Training Program is an Essential part for employee & Organization?	111	74.00	39	26.00

Source:- Survey Data

95% and above respondents are suggested that, training program helps to improve the Motivation level , enhance their skill, Knowledge and attitude which can help the productive of the company.

90 % to 95 % respondents stated that, Training Program helps to achieve the goals and objective of the company. the companies have the specific policy to provide the training program which enhance the skill and knowledge. It enhances the Motivation and it helps to develop the behavioral skill and knowledge.

85-90 % of the respondents are stated that the companies are arranged the suitable program to motivate their employee and get updated knowledge. Motivation is a part to enhance the productivity which is an essential part of the employee as well as the organization.

80-85 % respondents stated that, the training results to make more productive, and the company have the policy to measure the training program.

74 % respondents stated that, Training program is an essential part for the employee as well as the organization.

Table 2:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector

Descriptive								
Rating	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Below 20 Years	10	7.4000	.69921	.22111	6.8998	7.9002	6.00	8.00
21-30 Years	26	7.6923	1.34964	.26469	7.1472	8.2374	5.00	9.00

Descriptive								
Rating	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
31-40 Years	54	7.7963	1.40591	.19132	7.4126	8.1800	5.00	10.00
41-50 Years	43	7.6279	1.55874	.23771	7.1482	8.1076	3.00	9.00
51 Years & Above	17	7.5882	1.32565	.32152	6.9066	8.2698	5.00	9.00
Total	150	7.6800	1.38700	.11325	7.4562	7.9038	3.00	10.00

Source:- Survey Data

Table 3:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (ANOVA Test for Age Group)

ANOVA					
Rating	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.778	4	.445	.226	.923
Within Groups	284.862	145	1.965		
Total	286.640	149			

Source:- Survey Data

P value is obtained as 0.923 (>0.05), thus it concluded that there is **no** significant difference between respondents of different age groups with regard to satisfaction with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector

Table 4:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (Descriptive for Age group)

Descriptives								
Rating	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Below 20 Years	10	10.0000	.00000	.00000	10.0000	10.0000	10.00	10.00
21-30 Years	26	9.0769	.84489	.16570	8.7357	9.4182	8.00	10.00
31-40 Years	54	8.8148	1.06530	.14497	8.5240	9.1056	7.00	10.00
41-50 Years	43	8.9302	1.24203	.18941	8.5480	9.3125	6.00	10.00
51 Years & Above	17	8.7647	1.39326	.33792	8.0484	9.4811	6.00	10.00
Total	150	8.9667	1.11978	.09143	8.7860	9.1473	6.00	10.00

Source:- Survey Data

Table 5:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (ANOVA Test for Age Group)

ANOVA					
Rating	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12.990	4	3.247	2.709	.033
Within Groups	173.844	145	1.199		
Total	186.833	149			

Source:- Survey Data

P value is obtained as 0.033 (< 0.05), thus it concluded that there is a significant difference between respondents of different age groups with regard to satisfaction with respect Effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector

Table 67:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (Descriptive for Gender)

Group Statistics					
	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Rating	Male	108	7.7222	1.42628	.13724
	Female	42	7.5714	1.29054	.19914

Source:- Survey Data

Table 7:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (T Test for Gender)

Independent Samples Test											
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means							
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
										Lower	Upper
Rating	Equal variances assumed	1.130	.290	.597	148	.552	.15079	.25277	-.34871	.65030	
	Equal variances not assumed			.624	82.102	.535	.15079	.24185	-.33031	.63190	

P value is obtained as 0.552 (>0.05), thus it concluded that there is **no** significant difference between respondents of Male and Female with regard to Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector

Table 8:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (Descriptive for Gender group)

Group Statistics					
	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Rating	Male	108	9.0556	1.16678	.11227
	Female	42	8.7381	.96423	.14878

Source:- Survey Data

Table 9:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (T Test for Gender)

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Rating	Equal variances assumed	1.124	.291	1.567	148	.119	.31746	.20264	-.08299	.71791
	Equal variances not assumed			1.703	89.827	.092	.31746	.18639	-.05285	.68777

Source:- Survey Data

P value is obtained as 0.119 (>0.05), thus it concluded that there is **no** significant difference between respondents of different male and female groups with regard to satisfaction with respect Effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector

Table 10:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (Descriptive for Qualification group)

Descriptive								
Rating								
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Under Graduate	10	7.4000	.69921	.22111	6.8998	7.9002	6.00	8.00
Graduate	88	7.6364	1.34917	.14382	7.3505	7.9222	5.00	10.00
Post Graduate	26	7.7308	1.71015	.33539	7.0400	8.4215	3.00	10.00
Above Post Graduate	26	7.8846	1.39505	.27359	7.3211	8.4481	5.00	9.00
Total	150	7.6800	1.38700	.11325	7.4562	7.9038	3.00	10.00

Source:- Survey Data

Table 11:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Effective of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (ANOVA Test for Qualification Group)

ANOVA					
Rating					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.107	3	.702	.360	.782
Within Groups	284.533	146	1.949		
Total	286.640	149			

Source:- Survey Data

P value is obtained as 0.782 (>0.05), thus it concluded that there is **no** significant difference between respondents of different qualification group with regard to satisfaction with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector

Table 12:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (Descriptive for Qualification group)

Descriptive								
Rating								
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Under Graduate	10	10.0000	.00000	.00000	10.0000	10.0000	10.00	10.00
Graduate	88	8.8636	1.04146	.11102	8.6430	9.0843	6.00	10.00
Post Graduate	26	8.8462	1.31734	.25835	8.3141	9.3782	6.00	10.00
Above Post Graduate	26	9.0385	1.21592	.23846	8.5473	9.5296	6.00	10.00
Total	150	8.9667	1.11978	.09143	8.7860	9.1473	6.00	10.00

Source:- Survey Data

Table 13:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (ANOVA Test for Qualification Group)

ANOVA					
Rating					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12.124	3	4.041	3.377	.020
Within Groups	174.710	146	1.197		
Total	186.833	149			

Source:- Survey Data

P value is obtained as 0.020 (<0.05), thus it concluded that there is a significant difference between respondents of different qualification group with regard to satisfaction with respect Effective Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector.

Table 14:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector.(Descriptive for Technical Qualification)

Group Statistics					
	Technical Qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Rating	42	6.9524	1.18841	.18338	42
	108	7.9630	1.35981	.13085	108

Source:- Survey Data

Table 15:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (T Test for Technical Qualification)

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper

Rating	Equal variances assumed	.209	.648	-4.227	148	.000	-1.01058	.23905	-1.48298	-.53819
	Equal variances not assumed			-4.486	84.942	.000	-1.01058	.22527	-1.45849	-.56268

Source:- Survey Data

P value is obtained as 0.000 (<0.05), thus it concluded that there is a significant difference between respondents of having Technical Qualification with regard to satisfaction with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector.

Table 16:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (Descriptive for Technical Qualification)

Group Statistics					
	Technical Qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Rating	Yes	42	8.3810	1.01097	.15600
	No	108	9.1944	1.08048	.10397

Source:- Survey Data

Table 17:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Rating	Equal variances assumed	.029	.864	-4.214	148	.000	-.81349	.19307	-1.19501	-.43197
	Equal variances not assumed			-4.339	79.504	.000	-.81349	.18747	-1.18660	-.44038

Source:- Survey Data

P value is obtained as 0.000 (<0.05), thus it concluded that there is a significant difference between respondents of having Technical Qualification with regard to satisfaction with respect effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector.

Table 18:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (Descriptive for Experience group)

Descriptive								
Rating	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Below 5 Years					51	7.5098		
6-10 Years	25	7.0800	1.55242	.31048	6.4392	7.7208	5.00	10.00
11-15 Years	42	7.7857	1.40618	.21698	7.3475	8.2239	3.00	9.00
16-20 Years	12	8.7500	.86603	.25000	8.1998	9.3002	6.00	9.00
20 Years Above	20	8.0000	1.21395	.27145	7.4319	8.5681	5.00	9.00
Total	150	7.6800	1.38700	.11325	7.4562	7.9038	3.00	10.00

Source:- Survey Data

Table 19:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector. (ANOVA Test for Experience Group)

ANOVA					
Rating					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	26.733	4	6.683	3.729	.006
Within Groups	259.907	145	1.792		
Total	286.640	149			

Source:- Survey Data

P value is obtained as 0.006 (<0.05), thus it concluded that there is a significant difference between respondents of different Experience group with regard to satisfaction with respect of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector.

Table 20:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector (Descriptive for Experience group)

Descriptive								
Rating								
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Below 5 Years	51	9.2745	.96080	.13454	9.0043	9.5447	7.00	10.00
6-10 Years	25	8.3200	1.28193	.25639	7.7908	8.8492	6.00	10.00

11-15 Years	42	8.8571	1.13849	.17567	8.5024	9.2119	6.00	10.00
16-20 Years	12	9.5000	.52223	.15076	9.1682	9.8318	9.00	10.00
20 Years Above	20	8.9000	1.16529	.26057	8.3546	9.4454	6.00	10.00
Total	150	8.9667	1.11978	.09143	8.7860	9.1473	6.00	10.00

Source:- Survey Data

Table 21:- Satisfaction of Respondents on Current Company with respect of effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector (ANOVA Test for Experience Group)

ANOVA					
Rating					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	19.294	4	4.823	4.174	.003
Within Groups	167.540	145	1.155		
Total	186.833	149			

Source:- Survey Data

P value is obtained as 0.003 (<0.05), thus it concluded that there is a significant difference between respondents of different Experience group with regard to satisfaction with respect of Effectiveness of Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector.

With regards to the results of T Test and ANOVA it is found that, satisfaction of the respondents with different demographic profile is a significantly different. Thus Null Hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that, there is an impact of demographic factors on satisfaction and its effectiveness on Impact of Training & Development on Motivation, Employee Performance & Productivity in the Context of Manufacturing Sector

- a. The average level of the satisfaction of the training program with respect of the training program arranged by the company was **7.68** (out of 10) and its effectiveness average is **8.97** (out of 10). It indicates that the Impact of Training and Development program is effective on the performance and productivity in the context of Manufacturing sector.
- b. It is observed that the factors of the demographic factor in Gender (Mean- 7.64) and Technical qualification (Mean-7.45) are in below average and other factors are same with respect of Level of satisfaction and the demographic factors in Age, Qualification, Experience (Mean- 8.96) are near about the average of total average and Technical Qualification (Mean-8.78) are in below average with respect of Effectiveness on Motivation and satisfaction level in manufacturing company.

Table 22:- Demographic Profile of Respondents

Age Group	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)	Year of Experience	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Below 20 Years	10	6.67	Below 5 Years	51	34.00
21-30	26	17.33	6-10 Years	25	16.67
31-40	54	36.00	11-15 Years	42	28.00
41-50	43	28.67	16-20 Years	12	8.00
51 Years & Above	17	11.33	20 Years above	20	13.33
Total	150	100.00	Total	150	100.00
Technical Qualification	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)	Gender	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	42	28.00	Male	108	72.00
No	108	72.00	Female	42	28.00
Total	150	100.00	Total	150	100.00
Qualification	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)			
Under Graduate	10	6.67			
Graduate	88	58.67			
Post Graduate	26	17.33			
Above Post Graduate	26	17.33			
Total	150	100.00			

Source:- Survey Data

FINDINGS & SUGGESTIONS

1. 95% above respondents stated that training program helps to improve the Motivation, Enhance the Skills, Knowledge and attitude and behavior which helps the productivity of the company. Hence it is proved that Training program is an important factor for the organization and it should be arranged in a proper manner for the employee.
2. 91-94 % of the employees suggested that Training and development helps the company to achieve more productivity to achieve the goal and the company has the policy to provide the training program for the employee. This means the company should arrange the effective training program to motivate the employee and for productivity.
3. 90% respondents stated that motivation helps to improve the performance. Hence it is suggested that, the company should focus on the motivation factor of the employee.
4. 74% of the respondents stated that, Training Program is an Essential part for employee & Organization? The respondents having 16-20 Years of experienced respondents have given the statement. Means the experienced person states that it is good for the organization.
5. It is observed that, there is no significant difference between respondents of different factors except experience factor related to level of motivation and their satisfaction. For effectiveness on motivation of different demographic factors in Gender group. Hence it is suggested that, training program should be well planned for the employee which helps to performance and productivity as well.
6. It concluded that there is a significant difference between respondents of different Age, Qualification, Technical qualification and experience group with regard to satisfaction with respect Effective impact of Training and Development on employee Performance and Productivity. Hence it is suggested that the training program should be arranged as and should be more effective.

CONCLUSION:

Impact of the training and its effectiveness plays in different aspects in performance in the organization. The effectiveness of the training program must be covered the major areas like, soft skill development, behavioral changes, personality development, motivation, managerial and supervisory skill. The basic objective to arrange the training program is to motivate the employee and develop the skill which will be impact upon their performance. By the result the productivity

comes out. The organization needs to focus on the training program for the growth of the organization. In any organization motivation impact the employee performance basically those who have less skill and are motivated and more and more contribute for their performance. Employee job satisfaction depends upon the motivation and how the employee performs in the organization basically in Manufacturing sector. It plays a vital role in the making of profit and also increases the productivity of workers. The study proves the impact of training and development on Motivation and employee performance. Training and development upgrade not only the productivity of employees but also of the organization. It has rightly been said, employee development is the key to organizational sustainable development. Organizations must have employees who are able to quickly adapt to an ever-changing world market. Manufacturing Companies need to invest in on-going employee training and development in order to both keep employees and be successful. Training enhances employees' initiative and quality of work, thereby assisting them to be more committed to achieving the organizational goals and objectives and in turn enhancing employees' effectiveness within the organization. Continuous improvement is highly effective on the performance of the employee. The different kinds of training program truly jobs the employee to acquire the new knowledge and develop the new and updated skill which the employee can perform their job in a better way. Therefore learning and development is vital to the productivity of organization's workforce.

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